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Pore forming properties of alamethicin in negatively charged floating bilayer lipid membranes supported on gold electrodes

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Abstract

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS), atomic force microscopy (AFM) and photon polarization infrared reflection absorption spectroscopy (PM-IRRAS) were employed to investigate the formation of alamethicin pores in negatively charged bilayers composed of a mixture of DMPC and Egg-PG floating at gold (111) electrode surfaces modified by self-assembled monolayers of 1-thio- β -D-glucose (β -Tg). The EIS data showed that presence of alamethicin decreases the membrane resistivity by about one order of magnitude. PM-IRRAS measurements provided information about the tilt angles of peptide helical axis with respect to the bilayer normal. Small tilt angle values of the peptide prove that the alamethicin molecules were inserted into the DMPC/Egg-PG membranes. The tilt angles decreased when negative potentials were applied, which correlates with the observed decrease in membrane resistivity, indicating that ion pore formation is assisted by the transmembrane potential. Molecular-resolution AFM images provided visual evidence that alamethicin molecules aggregate forming hexagonal porous 2D lattices with periodicities of 2.0 ± 0.2 nm. The pore formation by alamethicin in the negatively charged membrane was compared to the interaction of this peptide with a bilayer formed by zwitterionic lipids. The comparison of these results showed that alamethicin preferentially forms ion translocating pores in negatively charged phospholipid membranes.

Introduction

The number of antibiotic resistant bacterial strains is currently on the rise due to over-prescription and improper disposal of antibiotic medications. To combat this growing concern, novel antimicrobial therapeutics have been intensively investigated during the last two decades.^{1, 2} One class of therapeutics are antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), which target the cell membrane of the pathogen by forming ion conducting transmembrane pores.³ Several models have been proposed for AMP pores formed in lipid bilayers, which include the toroidal or worm-like structure, barrel-stave, and carpet models.^{4,5} The pore formation results in leakage of ions and other metabolites, loss of cytoplasmic components and dissipation of electrostatic potential, leading to the cell death.^{4,5}

Alamethicin (Alm) is a popular peptide used to study pore formation in biomimetic membranes. Alamethicin is a 20-residue antibiotic peptide isolated from *Trichoderma viride* and crystallographic data shows that it adopts a helical structure with α -helix at the N-terminus transitioning to a 3_{10} -helix after 14th amino acid residue.^{6, 7} The angle between the α -helix and 3_{10} -helix axes is 25°. A single alamethicin molecule can be modeled as a cylinder with diameter of 1.1 nm and length of 3.2 nm.⁷ Alm molecules are active against Gram-positive bacteria and fungi.^{6,8} The membraneolytic activity of Alm depends on temperature, peptide concentration, peptide/lipid (P/L) molar ratio, and lipid bilayer composition. The Alm peptides can either bind to the lipid bilayer surface (inactive state) or insert into the membranes core (active state).^{9,10,11} It is widely accepted that in the inserted state, the Alm molecules act as individual staves forming a water-filled barrel-like pore.^{7,8,12}

Alm has been extensively studied in recent years. He et al. applied neutron in-plane scattering to show that inserted Alm monomers form large, well-defined pores in dilaurylphosphatidylcholine (DLPC) lipid membranes.¹³ Molecular dynamics simulations have been used to analyze the size of the alamethicin bundles in palmitoyloleoylphosphatidylcholine (POPC) bilayers.¹⁴ The results of these simulations suggest that alamethicin pores consisting of only four helices cannot form stable water-filled channels and that the hexamer pore model is the most energetically favorable structure. Low temperature electron spin-echo spectroscopy measurements demonstrated that alamethicin interacts differently with saturated and unsaturated lipids at cryogenic temperatures where both lipid bilayers are in a gel state.¹⁵ X-ray scattering has also been used to investigate the size of the Alm bundles in two unsaturated phospholipid membranes of differing chain length. In 1,2-dioleoyl-*sn*-glycero-

phosphatidylcholine (DOPC) bilayers alamethicin formed pentameric pores with an outer radius of 1.36 nm, while in bilayers of 1,2-dierucoyl-sn-glycero phosphatidylcholine (DEPC) nonamer channels were formed with an outer radius of 1.96 nm.¹⁶ Quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation monitoring (QCM-D) demonstrated that the insertion of Alm peptides into bilayer of egg phosphatidylcholine (Egg-PC) initially caused disordering of lipids. When equilibrium state of the insertion was reached, the lipids become more ordered.¹⁷ The combined NMR and MD results portray Alm as a flexible entity that preferentially adopts a transmembrane configuration in the fluid membrane environment.¹⁸

Insertion of alamethicin into biomimetic membranes was investigated by several IR spectroscopic techniques, such as attenuated total internal reflection ATR, sum-frequency generation (SFG)^{19–22}, surface enhanced infrared reflection absorption spectroscopy (SEIRAS)²³ and photon polarization infrared reflection absorption spectroscopy.^{24,25} Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) provides unique information about conductivity of biomimetic membranes with incorporated ion channels.²⁶ This technique has been used to study the incorporation of Alm into bilayers supported at electrode surfaces on mercury^{27,28} and on gold.^{24,25,29} The images of the barrel-stave type aggregates of alamethicin molecules in a phospholipid monolayer supported at a gold electrode was obtained by electrochemical scanning tunneling microscopy³⁰ and more recently in a floating phospholipid bilayer by atomic force microscopy.²⁹

The majority of these studies were concerned with incorporation of alamethicin into membranes composed of zwitterionic phospholipids, which resemble the composition of mammalian cell membranes. However, alamethicin is antibiotic peptide acting on negatively charged membranes of bacteria. The cytotoxic properties of antibiotic peptides depend on the negative charge on a membrane.³¹ Therefore, this paper will describe the voltage-gated behavior of alamethicin in a floating bilayer membrane (fBLM) composed of a mixture of negatively charged egg-PG and zwitterionic DMPC phospholipids. Egg-PG was used, rather than DMPG as in our previous study,²⁹ to improve membrane fluidity. In addition, the same mixture of DMPC and Egg-PG was used in the STM studies of pores formed in the monolayer of lipids.³⁰ High resolution STM images of the pores formed in the monolayer will be used as a reference for interpretation of the AFM images acquired for the floating bilayer in this work. Our objective is to compare the insertion of Alm peptides into negatively charged phospholipid bilayers to the

previously studied zwitterionic bilayers.²⁵ This work employs AFM to provide visual images of the alamethicin channels in the floating bilayer and EIS to determine changes in the membrane conductivity induced by the formation of Alamion channels. Complementary PM-IRRAS data provides quantitative information concerning the peptide orientation and conformation, allowing molecular level interpretation of the voltage-induced changes of the membrane conductivity of ion channels. This study contributes new knowledge about the effect of charge on the membrane on the insertion of the antibiotic peptide and provides a basis for studying the effect of amiloride, an ion channel blocker, on the formation of alamethicin pores. The effect of amiloride will be described in our next publication.

Experimental Section

Chemicals and Solutions. 1,2-Dimyristoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DMPC) and L- α -phosphatidylglycerol sodium salt derived from chicken eggs (Egg-PG) were purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids (99% pure; Alabaster, AL, US), and alamethicin (Alm) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, US). The phospholipids were used as purchased without further purification. HPLC-grade chloroform purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, US) was used to prepare vesicle solutions. Sodium fluoride powder, 99% purity (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, US), was cleaned in a UV-ozone chamber (Jelight, Irvine, CA, US) for 20 min to oxidize and remove any organic impurities prior to use. The NaF electrolyte solutions were prepared by dissolving the pre-cleaned powder in Milli-Q UV plus ultra-pure, 18.2 M Ω cm, water (EMD Millipore, Billerica, MA, US) to give final concentrations of 100 mM for the EIS and PM-IRRAS experiments and 1 mM for AFM imaging.

Sample Preparation and Bilayer formation. All glassware was cleaned in a hot mixed acid bath (1 part HNO₃: 3 parts H₂SO₄) for 60 min and then thoroughly rinsed and soaked in Milli-Q water for 3-4 hrs. The Teflon pieces were soaked in a Piranha solution (1 part H₂O₂: 3 parts H₂SO₄) and then rinsed with Milli-Q ultra-pure water.

The gold substrates used in the AFM studies were produced in the AXXIS co-sputtering deposition system (Kurt J. Lesker, (Jefferson Hills, PA, US) by magnetron sputtering technique (Torus, 3" dia., DC). Titanium adhesion layers (3 - 5 nm thickness) were first deposited onto clean glass microscope slides. Next, gold films (~200 nm) were deposited onto the titanium

adhesion layers to create stable and highly uniform gold substrates. The gold-coated glass slides were then annealed in a muffle furnace at 675 °C for 70 seconds to produce large and well-ordered gold crystallites. The gold slides were then immersed into a 2 mM aqueous solution of 1-thio- β -D-glucose (β -Tg) for 20 h, to create a uniform self-assembled monolayer (SAM). The β -Tg SAM is very hydrophilic and creates a conditioning layer that assists in the fusion of vesicles forming bilayers and provides a water rich environment on both sides of the bilayer better mimicking biological membranes. Afterwards, the β -Tg-modified gold (111) surface was rinsed with copious amounts of water to remove residual β -Tg molecules.

Stock solutions of DMPC, Egg-PG and alamethicin were prepared by dissolving each individual powder in chloroform giving final concentrations of 4.54, 10 and 2 mg/ml, respectively. The appropriate concentration of each stock solution was then combined in a single test tube and solvent was slowly evaporated by vortexing the mixture under a stream of argon producing a dried film of either DMPC/Egg-PG (1:1 molar ratio) or DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm (9:9:2 molar ratio). The test tubes containing the dried films were placed in a desiccator for at least 24 h prior to use to assure that the chloroform was completely removed. The vesicles were then formed in the test tube by adding 1 ml Milli-Q water to the dry lipid film to give a final concentration of 1 mg/ml. The mixture was sonicated for 30 min at 35 °C to ensure that vesicles of an appropriate size and distribution were formed in water.

A single crystal gold (111) electrode with a surface area of 0.172 cm² was prepared in accordance to the procedure described in ³² and used as the working electrode for the electrochemical and PM-IRRAS measurements.³² The working electrode was flame-annealed with a Bunsen burner and cooled before placing it into beaker containing 2 mM Tg SAM solution for 20 h. After removing the electrode from the β -Tg SAM, the modified gold (111) electrode rinsed with sufficient amounts of Milli-Q water. Next, the gold slides or gold (111) electrode were transferred to a beaker containing mixed vesicles and incubated for 12 h to ensure that uniform bilayers with minimal defects are deposited onto the modified electrode surface.

AFM measurements. Dynamic MAC mode AFM images were acquired with an Agilent Technologies 5500 Scanning Probe Microscope (Agilent N9621-13601 MAC III Mode controller, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, US) in a 1 mM NaF solution. All images were recorded at 21 \pm 0.5 °C using type VII MAC cantilevers (Keysight Technologies,

Mississauga, ON, CA) with nominal spring constant of 0.14 N/m and resonance frequency of 8 - 10 kHz in solution. The AFM scanner (model N9520A-US07480132) was calibrated with 145-nm Pitch calibration standard for AFM (Ted Pella Inc, Redding, CA, US) prior to imaging. The topography, amplitude and phase images were simultaneously recorded at a scan speed between 2.0 to 3.5 lines per second. The system was allowed to stabilize for a minimum of 30 min before acquiring AFM images. Data acquisition and analysis were carried out using PicoView 1.49 (Agilent Technologies, Mississauga, ON, CA) and Gwyddion v2.40 (Czech Metrology Institute, Brno, CZ) software, respectively.

The force versus distance curve measurements were carried out in solution using V-shape silicon nitride cantilevers with spring constants of $\sim 0.06 \text{ N m}^{-1}$. The exact value was determined by thermal tune method prior to each experiment. Force spectroscopy curves were recorded by measuring the deflection of the cantilever versus the position of the Z-piezo of the scanner. The time required to record a single force-distance curve was 1.59 seconds where the total distance traveled by the tip was $\sim 400 \text{ nm}$ (approach and retraction). The cantilever deflection versus piezo position curves were converted to force-distance curves (force vs. tip-substrate distance) using software that was written in-house. For statistical data analysis, a minimum of 100 measurements were performed. A home-made EC-AFM cell was employed for potential dependent studies where a gold wire was used the counter electrode and an oxidized gold wire was used as the reference electrode. The gold wires were cleaned in piranha solutions and rinsed by copious amount of water. Next the gold wire was oxidized at $E = 1.1 \text{ V}$ vs Ag/AgCl in 0.1M NaF for a period of 30 min to create the gold oxide reference electrode. The open circuit potential (OCP) of the gold wire covered with gold oxide was 0.66 vs Ag/AgCl. The OCP of the oxide coated gold wire was measured before and after the experiment to ensure that the reference potential was stable. In a 24 h test experiment, the reference voltage of the gold oxide reference dropped from 0.66 V to 0.62 V vs Ag/AgCl. The potentials were applied to the working electrode (i.e. gold coated glass slide) using a potentiostat/galvanostat (HEKA PG590, Pfalz, DE).

Electrochemical instrumentation and measurements. The electrochemical measurements were carried out in an all-glass three-electrode cell consisting of a gold (111) working electrode, a coiled gold wire as the counter electrode and a saturated Ag/AgCl reference electrode (sat. KCl, +240 mV vs. SHE). The electrochemical cell was deaerated by purging with argon for 30

minutes prior to any measurements. The modified gold (111) crystal face was horizontally touched to the supporting electrolyte and then slowly raised to attain a hanging meniscus configuration where only the single crystal surface was in contact with the electrolyte solution. To prevent the influx of oxygen, an argon blanket was maintained above the solution throughout the duration of the experiment. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was performed using the Solartron SI 1287 electrochemical interface (Ametek Scientific Instruments, Oakridge, TN, US) and Solartron SI 1260 impedance/gain-phase analyzer (Ametek Scientific Instruments, Oakridge, TN, US). EIS spectra were collected in the frequency range from 10^{-3} to 10^3 Hz with a bias potential of 0.1 V vs Ag/AgCl electrode and excitation amplitude of 0.005 V. Data processing of the EIS results was conducted using the ZView software (Scribner Associates Inc., Brno, CZ). Differential capacitance measurements were performed using a computer-controlled system, consisting of a PG590 potentiostat/galvanostat (HEKA, Pfalz, DE) and a lock-in amplifier (EG&G Instruments 7265 DSP, Wellesley, MA, US). Custom software was used to collect electrochemical data. The DC curves were measured using a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} superimposed on an ac perturbation with a frequency of 25 Hz and rms amplitude of 5 mV. The capacitance was calculated from the in-phase and out-of-phase components of the ac signal treating the electrochemical interface as a capacitor and resistor in series (RC circuit). The immersion method was employed to determine the potential of zero free charge (E_{pzfc}) of the DMPC/Egg-PG and DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm bilayers floating on the β -Tg modified gold (111) surface.³³ Figure S1 of the Supporting Information shows two representative current transients measured when the β -Tg modified gold (111) electrode covered by the DMPC/Egg-PG bilayers in the absence and presence of Alm were brought in contact with the 0.1 M sodium fluoride electrolyte solution at a controlled immersion potential. Figure S2 of the Supporting Information plots the free charge versus electrode potential determined by integration of these transients. The potentials of zero free charge obtained from these plots amount to 0.11 and 0.13 V vs Ag/AgCl for the electrode covered with bilayer without and with alamethicin, respectively.

PM-IRRAS measurements and data processing. PM-IRRAS experiments were performed using a Thermo Nicolet Nexus 870 spectrometer equipped with an external tabletop optical mount (TOM) box. An electrochemical IR cell equipped with 1 in. CaF_2 equilateral prism (BoXin, Changchun, CN) was used in the IR experiment. The prism was washed with methanol

and pure water, and then cleaned in the UV ozone chamber for 15 min prior to mounting it on the electrochemical cell. The half-wave retardation of the photoelastic modulator (PEM) was set to 1600 cm^{-1} and an angle of incidence was set to 60° for the amide I band region to obtain a large enhancement of the mean square electric field strength (MSEFS). D_2O was selected as solvent to avoid spectral overlap by the IR absorption of H_2O . 4000 IR scans were collected and averaged with the instrumental resolution of 4 cm^{-1} for each potential ranging from 0.1 and -1.0 V vs Ag/AgCl (sat.). The average and the difference signals from the detector were corrected for the PEM response functions as described in ref.^{34,35} The signal obtained (ΔS) is proportional to the absorbance (A) of the molecules adsorbed at the electrode surface, as defined by:

$$\Delta S = \frac{2(I_s - I_p)}{(I_s + I_p)} = 2.3A = 2.3\Gamma\varepsilon \quad (1)$$

where I_s and I_p are the intensities of the s- and p-polarized radiation, Γ is the surface concentration of the adsorbed species and ε is the decimal molar absorption coefficient of the adsorbed species.

The average tilt angles of the 3_{10} -helix and α -helix of the alamethicin molecule with respect to the gold surface normal were calculated from the integrated intensity of the corresponding vibration bands in the experimentally measured PM-IRRAS spectra as described in ref.²⁴ The PM-IRRAS spectra of the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm bilayer with randomly oriented molecules was simulated according to a model parallel homogeneous layers (gold/(DMPC/Egg-PG /Alm)/ $\text{D}_2\text{O}/\text{CaF}_2$) and a custom written software that solves the Fresnel equations employing the transfer matrix method.^{34,35} The optical constants of gold, D_2O and CaF_2 were obtained from literature.³⁶⁻³⁸ The optical constants of the DMPC/Egg-PG /Alm mixture were measured from the transmission IR experiment of a dispersion of vesicles. The optical constants are presented in Figure S3 of the Supporting Information. The thickness of the DMPC/Egg-PG /Alm bilayer was determined by AFM to be equal to 4.3 nm.

Results

Electrochemical Data

Initially, differential capacitance (DC) measurements were used to characterize the stability of the DMPC/Egg-PG bilayers in the absence and presence of Alm. Figure 1 compares the measured capacitance values of the pure gold (111) electrode in the supporting electrolyte (1), the electrode covered by the SAM of β -Tg (2), the deposited DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer (3) and DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm (4) as a function of the applied potential.

Figure 1. Differential capacitance measurements of the film-free gold electrode (1-blue), β -Tg SAM modified gold electrode (2-magenta), floating DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer (3-black) and floating DMPC/Egg-PG /Alm bilayer on the Tg-modified gold electrode surfaces (4-red) recorded at a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} , frequency 25 Hz and 5 mV rms ac amplitude in a 0.1 M NaF electrolyte.

The differences in the capacitance curves of the floating DMPC/Egg-PG bilayers in the absence and presence of 10% of alamethicin are small suggesting that both films are successfully deposited onto the surface of the Tg-SAM. The minimum capacitance of both mixed bilayers is $\sim 7.5 \text{ } \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$ for potential window ranging from -0.4 to 0 V vs. Ag/AgCl suggesting that stable and densely packed bilayers with small defect densities are formed on the Tg-modified gold surface. At potentials more negative than -0.4 V vs Ag/Ag/Cl, the capacitance increases more rapidly indicating onset of electrodedwetting of the bilayer from the electrode surface. The maximum in the capacitance at $\sim -0.9 \text{ V vs Ag/AgCl}$ indicates that the bilayers are

desorbed/detached from the electrode surface. The position of this maximum correlates well with the maximum on the DC curve for the gold electrode covered by a SAM of β -Tg, indicating that desorption/detachment of the membrane coincides with the desorption of the SAM of β -Tg. At potentials more negative than -1.1V vs Ag/AgCl, the capacitance curves for the floating bilayer covered electrodes merge with the curve obtained for the film-free gold electrode, indicating that the complete desorption (dewetting) of the bilayer and reductive desorption of the thioglucose SAM have taken place. For the anodic potentials, both film covered electrodes display a small maximum in capacitance at 0.2V vs AgCl, which may correspond to either a reorientation within the film, partial detachment of β -Tg or penetration of anions from the supporting electrolyte. It should be noted that the capacitance of the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm bilayer is lower than the DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer prior to desorption, which implies that the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm film is slightly more stable and consists of fewer defects.

Figure 2. a) Absolute impedance values and b) corresponding phase angles of the floating DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer containing 10% alamethicin supported on the β -thioglucose modified gold (111) electrode. at selected applied voltages in a 0.1 M NaF electrolyte. The solid lines represent the fits of the experimental data to the equivalent circuit shown in Figure 2b at 0.1 V (black squares), -0.1V (red triangles), -0.2 V (green diamonds), -0.3 V (blue inverted triangles), and -0.4 V (magenta stars) vs Ag/AgCl reference electrode.

Differential capacitance plots were determined using a simplified equivalent circuit and hence provided qualitative characteristics of the interface in the presence of the bilayer only. More precise EIS measurements were performed, for the potentials range 0.1 to -0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl, corresponding to the well on the DC curves in Figure 1. The EIS measurements provided additional information about the effect of alamethicin on the bilayer resistance and consequently on the pore forming ability of alamethicin in the model membranes. Figure 2 presents the absolute values of the impedance (a) and the corresponding phase angle (b) collected for the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm bilayer for the potentials ranging from 0.1 V and -0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl and frequency range from 0.01 to 1000 Hz. The phase angle plots display a maximum at ~10 Hz. The decrease at higher frequencies is determined by the resistivity of the electrolyte. Valincius et al.²⁶ demonstrated that the decrease of the phase angle at lower frequencies is caused by defects or pores present in the bilayer. By moving the potential in negative direction, the maximum shifts slightly to lower frequencies indicating an increase in defects/ion channel density.

The solid lines in Figures 2 (a) and (b) show the fits of the experimental data to the equivalent circuit, shown in Figure 2 (b), proposed by Valincius et al.²⁶ In this circuit, R_s and R_m are resistances of the electrolyte solution and the bilayer (membrane) respectively, CPE_m and CPE_{sub} represent constant phase elements of the membrane and subphase that separates the floating bilayer from the gold electrode surface. The impedance of the constant phase element is described by the equation:

$$Z_{CPE} = \frac{1}{Q(j\omega)^\alpha} \quad (2)$$

where Q is the constant phase element coefficient measured in $\mu\text{F cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{\alpha-1}$ and α is related to the frequency dispersion. The numerical values of the elements of the equivalent circuit determined from the fit to experimental data are listed in Table 1.

The EIS measurements were also performed on the Au (111) electrode surface covered by a floating bilayer of DMPC/Egg-PG in the absence of alamethicin. Figure S4 of the Supporting Information plots the absolute values of the impedance and the corresponding phase angles. The numerical values of elements of the equivalent circuit used to fit these data are listed in Table S1 of the Supporting Information.

Table 1. Numerical values of the elements of the equivalent circuit of gold (111) electrode with DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm (9:9:2) bilayer at different potentials in 0.1M NaF solution fitted by equivalent circuit shown in Figure 2b.

Potential / V vs Ag/AgCl	$R_m / k\Omega$ cm^2	$CPE_m /$ $\mu F cm^{-2} s^{-\alpha-1}$	α_m	$CPE_{sub} /$ $\mu F cm^{-2} s^{-\alpha-1}$	α_{sub}
0.1	897 ± 85	9.4 ± 1.6	0.967 ± 0.001	1.0 ± 0.1	0.531 ± 0.018
-0.1	548 ± 74	10.6 ± 1.3	0.964 ± 0.002	1.2 ± 0.2	0.526 ± 0.017
-0.2	482 ± 30	12.2 ± 2.3	0.960 ± 0.004	1.5 ± 0.3	0.493 ± 0.016
-0.3	230 ± 54	15.1 ± 2.1	0.953 ± 0.002	1.6 ± 0.2	0.435 ± 0.017
-0.4	153 ± 24	19.1 ± 3.4	0.946 ± 0.001	2.5 ± 0.2	0.429 ± 0.013

The values of α_m are close to unity for all bilayers and at all potentials. Therefore, the values of the constant phase element Q_m , are representative of the membrane capacitance. Figure 3 (a) plots the Q_m values for the two different floating bilayers as a function of applied potential. Both curves display similar change with the electrode potential. However, the Q_m values are slightly lower when alamethicin is present. This suggests that the addition of the peptide to the film slightly improves the packing of lipids. The membrane resistance values, R_m , of the two different bilayers are plotted in Figure 3 (b). The membrane resistances of bilayers in the absence and presence of alamethicin are significant different. The data in Figure 3 (b) shows that the resistance decreases by more than an order of magnitude when alamethicin is incorporated into the bilayer. In addition, the changes of the membrane resistance with potential are more gradual when alamethicin is present. To gain a molecular level understanding of the effect of alamethicin of incorporation, AFM and PM-IRRAS techniques will be employed.

Figure 3. Variation in the (a) constant phase element (Q_m) and (b) membrane resistance (R_m) of the DMPC/Egg-PG (black rectangles) and DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm (red circle) bilayers floating on the β -Tg modified gold (111) surface as a function the applied potential in 0.1M NaF electrolyte.

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)

Imaging at OCP and Nanomechanical properties. Initially, the DMPC/Egg-PG floating bilayers were characterized at the open circuit potential of $\sim E = 0.1$ V vs Ag/AgCl. Figure 4 depicts the AFM topography and phase images of DMPC/Egg-PG bilayers deposited on the β -Tg-modified gold surfaces in the absence and presence of Alm

Figure 4. AFM topography (a, c) and phase (b, d) images of the pure DMPC/Egg-PG (1:1) [a, b] and DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm (9:9:2) [c, d] bilayers formed on the β -Tg-modified gold (111) electrode surfaces by vesicle fusion. The images were recorded at $E = 0.1$ V vs Ag/AgCl in 1 mM NaF solution using a scan size of 200×200 nm².

The topography image of the pure DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer presented in Figure 4 (a) shows faint reconstruction lines with a periodicity 8 ± 1 nm and 0.15 ± 0.05 nm rms roughness. These corrugations are somewhat smoother and have higher periodicity compared to the DMPC/DMPG

bilayers (periodicity 6.5 ± 1 nm and amplitude 0.25 ± 0.05 nm rms) previously measured by Abbasi et al.²⁹ The spontaneous curvature of the lipid molecules causes elastic stress in planar a bilayer which leads to formation of corrugations.³⁹ Apparently, the elastic stress is still present when DMPC is mixed with Egg-PG, although it is weaker than that of the DMPC/DMPG bilayers since the corrugation lines are broken. The phase image in Figure 4 (b) displays a mixture of bright and dark regions. These features suggest the formation of nano-domains or nanoclusters of different phase behavior. Figure 4 (c) shows that the corrugation lines largely disappear in the presence of alamethicin indicating that the peptide causes release of elastic stress. The gravel-like texture suggests nano-domains formation, however, the phase image in Figure 4 (d) shows uniform contrast suggesting that the bilayer components are no longer phase separated and exist in the same state.

The nanomechanical properties of the deposited bilayers were investigated using AFM force spectroscopy. Figure 5 (a) shows a typical force curve of a DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm bilayer formed onto β -Tg-modified gold surface. At the tip-sample separations less than 12 nm, repulsive interactions due primarily to coulombic and hydration forces between the cantilever tip and the bilayer dominate. When the tip-sample distance approaches 5 nm, a discontinuity is observed. The vertical increase of the force that follows the discontinuity corresponds to bending of the tip against a hard wall of the gold surface. The discontinuity in the force curve provides information about the thickness of the adsorbed film. Histograms of the “jump-in” distances from the force-distance curves of the DMPC/Egg-PG and DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm bilayers are presented in Figures 5 (b) and (c). The histograms were fit with a Gaussian distribution giving mean “jump-in” distances of 4.5 ± 0.6 nm for DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer and 4.6 ± 0.6 nm for the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm bilayer. Within experimental uncertainty, the widths of the “jump-in” distances are comparable for the two bilayers indicating that alamethicin has a minimal effect on the overall thickness of bilayer.

Figure 5. (a) A representative force-distance curve for the gold (111) electrode covered by DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer containing 10 mol % Alm deposited on a self-assembled monolayer of β -thioglucose measured in a 1 mM NaF electrolyte at temperature $22 \pm 2^\circ \text{C}$. Histograms of the width of the jump-in region on the force distance curves and penetration forces of the DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer in the absence (b, c) and presence of 10% of Alm bilayer (c, e) floating on the β -Tg modified gold surfaces.

Prior to tip penetration, the tip applies a compressive force to the bilayer surface causing its elastic deformation. The discontinuities on the force–distance curves give thickness values of the compressed bilayer that are smaller than the thicknesses of the bilayer that is not compressed. The elastic deformation, δ , produced by the AFM tip under a known load can be determined from the formula derived from Hertzian model⁴⁰:

$$\delta = \left(\frac{9F^2}{16RE^*} \right)^{1/3} \quad (3)$$

where R is the radius of the tip curvature (10 nm), F is the average penetration force (0.3 nN) and E^* is the effective compression modulus ($6.6 \times 10^7 \text{ N m}^{-2}$), which is determined from the Young modulus of a bilayer in liquid crystalline state.^{41–43} In the present case, the elastic deformation

amounts to 1 nm for DMPC/Egg-PG and 0.8 nm for DMPC/Egg-PG /Alm bilayers, which gives corrected thicknesses of $\sim 5.3 \pm 0.6$ nm and 5.6 ± 0.6 nm, respectively. These values are for a floating bilayer indicating that the DMPC/Egg-PG and DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm bilayers were formed at the gold (111) electrode surfaces.

Figures 5 (d and e) are histograms showing the bilayer penetration force. The penetration force is the force at which *N* elastically compressed molecules jump out from their equilibrium position in the bilayer to form a hole sufficient for the tip to penetrate the bilayer.^{44, 45} It is dependent on number of factors such as: the lateral interactions between the membrane molecules, chemical properties of the tip, the magnitude of the cantilever spring constant, the radius of the AFM tip and the approach velocity of the AFM tip.^{46,47,48} For the DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer, the average penetration force amounts to 0.3 ± 0.1 nN, while for the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm bilayer the average force is equal to 0.23 ± 0.11 nN. The small differences suggest that Alm has a small effect on nanomechanical properties of the bilayer. These values are comparable to those obtained for pure DMPC/DMPG and DMPC/DMPG/Alm bilayers (0.32 ± 0.17 nN and 0.30 ± 0.10 nN, respectively) measured in our previous paper under similar experimental conditions.²⁹ The low values of the penetration force indicate that the bilayers are in the liquid crystalline state.^{48,47} The distribution of penetration forces for the DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer is bimodal with a second small maximum observed at ~ 0.47 nN. This behavior agrees with the phase image in Figure 4 (a), which shows the segregation of nanometer sized domains within the bilayer film. The penetration force distribution for the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm bilayer is more symmetric indicating that addition of alamethicin improves the homogeneity of the mixed bilayer.

Potential dependent changes. Figure 6 illustrates the effect of potential on the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm bilayer structure when potential varies from 0.1 to -0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl, which corresponds to the range of potentials used in the EIS measurements. The phase images were selected for Figure 6 since they show improved contrast in the lateral domains over the topography images, which are presented in Figure S5 of the Supporting Information.

Figure 6. AFM phase images of the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm (9:9:2) bilayers at (a) 0.1, (b) -0.1, (c) -0.2, (d) -0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl recorded in 1 mM NaF solution. The scan size of all four images is 50 X 50 nm².

The high resolution images in Figure 6 show small changes in the bilayer structure. The lower resolution topography images in Figure S5 of the Supporting Information show that the morphology of the bilayer changes minimally within the potential range between 0.1 and -0.3 V vs Ag/AgCl. The roughness increases suddenly at E = -0.4V vs Ag/AgCl. This point is further

illustrated in Figure 7, which was recorded at a potential of 0.1 V and then stepped to a potential of -0.4 V at the region denoted by the dashed horizontal line.

Figure 7. AFM (a) topography and (b) phase images of the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm (9:9:2) bilayer formed on the Tg-modified gold (111) electrode surface by vesicle fusion. The regions above the dashed lines on the images were recorded at 0.1 V vs Ag/AgCl while the regions below the dashed lines were recorded at -0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl. The scan sizes of images are 168 X 168 nm².

The images in Figure 7 show that the bilayer is buckled at -0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl and become smooth at 0.1 V vs Ag/AgCl. Scaling analysis performed on the images in Figure S5 of the Supporting Information showed that the rms roughness (standard deviation of surface heights from the average height) of the bilayer at 0.1 V vs Ag/AgCl is equal to 155 ± 5 pm and increases to 320 ± 5 pm at -0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl. This behavior is consistent with previous neutron reflectivity⁴⁹ and AFM³⁹ measurements, which show that bilayer swelling occurs at potentials prior to film desorption. To verify these results, EIS data was collected at a potential of 0.1 V and then the EIS response was measured again at a potential of -0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl. The potential returned to 0.1V vs Ag/AgCl and the EIS was measured again. The results are shown in Figure S6 of the Supporting Information. The numerical values of the equivalent circuit elements obtained from the fitting of the experimental data to a model are presented in Table S2 of the Supporting Information. The data show that the membrane resistivity changes from 897 ± 85 k Ω

cm² to 153 ± 24 k Ω cm², when the potential is stepped from 0.1V to -0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl. However, the membrane resistance increases to a value of 1231 ± 132 k Ω cm² when the potential returns to 0.1 V vs Ag/AgCl, which is higher than the original value. This suggests that the penetration of water beneath the bilayer improves the fluidity of the membrane and assists in creating a more uniform and defect-free structure when the potential is returned to the more positive potentials. The AFM images show that applying a potential of -0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl causes the bilayer to swell and buckle. When the applied potential is 0.1 V vs Ag/AgCl, the bilayer returns to a flat and uniform structure, in good agreement with the EIS results.

The images in Figure 6 have sufficiently high resolution to reveal molecular structure of the bilayer. The enlarged images of the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm at 0.1 V and -0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl are shown in Figures 8 (a) and (f), respectively. The contrast reveals irregular molecular clusters resembling rows of phospholipid molecules and hexagonal-like aggregates suggesting the presence of transmembrane pores. Zoomed regions from within the marked areas of the bilayer at 0.1 V are presented in Figures 8 (b) and (c) and the marked areas of the bilayer at -0.4 V are displayed in Figures 8 (g) and (h). These enlarged images show two distinct molecular structures where one corresponds to a cluster of pores formed by the inclusion of 10% Alm and the other structure corresponds to the tightly packed, liquid-crystalline DMPC/Egg-PG molecules. The cross-sectional height profiles in Figure 8 (b) and (g) show the periodicity of honeycomb shaped clusters in the bilayers at the two voltages. The cross-sectional profiles were also measured from other similar looking aggregates in Figures 8 (a) and (f) giving an average periodicity of 2.0 ± 0.2 nm for these porous features. The honeycomb clusters have the appearance and periodicity expected for aggregates of alamethicin molecules forming pores in the phospholipid bilayer. The structures resemble barrel-stave pores created by individual alamethicin molecules as predicted by molecular dynamic simulations.^{50,51} These structures were also observed for alamethicin imbedded into DMPC/DMPG bilayers by Abbasi et al.²⁹ and in the STM images of DMPC/Egg-PG monolayers obtained by Pieta et al.³⁰

The contrast in Figures 8 (c) and (h) show a second molecular domain structure, which consists of hexagonally packed clusters of brighter spots in the phospholipid matrix. Figures 8 (e) and (j) show line profiles taken along the single rows in the hexagonal clusters. Similar cross-sectional

Figures 8. Enlarged phase images of the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm (9:9:2) bilayer formed on the Tg-modified gold (111) electrode at (a) 0.1 V and (f) -0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl, respectively; Magnified regions of the AFM images of the bilayers at 0.1 V [(b), (c)] and -0.4 V [(g), (h)], denoted by the marked squares showing cross-sectional height measurements [(d), (e), (i), (j)] of the phospholipid head groups and alamethicin pores. The images were acquired in 1 mM NaF solution.

profiles were taken from other locations in Figure 8 (a) and (f) giving an average periodicity of 1.7 ± 0.2 nm for the bright spots. This distance is comparable to the expected separation between the polar head groups of the phospholipid molecules.

In conclusion, the AFM images revealed that the honeycomb-shaped porous clusters formed by alamethicin are observed at all investigated potentials. At a potential of -0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl, bilayer swelling was observed, however, there was no appearance of nanometer-sized defects within the film formed at this negative potential. Unfortunately, high resolution images showing the pores could only be obtained from a small surface area preventing quantitative assessment of pores density and assessment of how the pores density changes with potential. To provide additional information about the potential induced changes in the structure and orientation of the alamethicin incorporated films, PM-IRRAS was employed.

PM-IRRAS experiments

Figure 9 (a) shows the PM-IRRAS spectra of the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm (9:9:2) bilayer formed on the β -Tg-modified gold (111) electrode. The bands at ~ 1730 cm^{-1} correspond to the C=O stretch of the lipid. The bands are red shifted with respect to the position of the band in the transmission spectrum of a solution of vesicles indicating that the polar heads of phospholipids are more hydrated in the floating bilayer. The bands in the $1700 - 1600$ cm^{-1} region correspond to amide I bands of alamethicin. Figure 9 (b) shows the deconvolution of these spectra into the individual vibrational components. The strong peak at ~ 1656 cm^{-1} is assigned to the α -helix, while the band at ~ 1633 cm^{-1} to the 3_{10} -helix. In addition, three small bands corresponding to β -sheet and β -turns are also present in this region. The centers of the α -helix, the 3_{10} -helix bands are somewhat shifted towards lower wave numbers with respect to the position of these bands in the solution of vesicles. Table 2 compares the band center positions in vesicles and in the floating bilayers for the DPhPC and DMPC/Egg-PG bilayers, containing 10 mol% of alamethicin.

Table 2 Peak centers of IR bands corresponding to α -helix and 3_{10} -helix of alamethicin in vesicles and bilayers of DPhPC and DMPC/Egg-PG.

	DPhPC vesicle	DPhPC bilayer	DMPC/Egg-PG vesicle	DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer
α -helix	1661 ± 2	1659 ± 2	1662 ± 2	1656 ± 2

3 ₁₀ -helix	1635 ± 2	1633 ± 2	1637 ± 2	1633 ± 2
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The two bands positions in vesicles of DPhPC and DMPC/Egg-PG are comparable. However, their positions in bilayers are systematically shifted towards lower wave numbers with respect to positions in vesicles. The difference is small for DPhPC but is more pronounced in the DMPC/Egg-PG system. The position of the amide I band in proteins to a large extent is determined by the dipole-dipole coupling between transition dipole moments of vibrating C=O groups in the amide bond.⁵² The red shift of the amide bands in bilayers indicates stronger dipole-dipole coupling and suggests that helices of the peptide are more ordered than in vesicles. The stronger red shift for the DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer suggests that alamethicin helices are somewhat better ordered in this environment. This may suggest that alamethicin molecules somewhat prefer planar rather than curved lipid bilayer. However, as stated earlier these shifts are small (almost within the limits of experimental uncertainties) indicating that only small changes in the hydrogen bonding in the helices takes place. Figure S7 of the Supporting Information plots dependence of the α -helix and 3₁₀-helix bands center as a function of the applied potential. Within the experimental errors, the positions of the bands centers are potential independent, indicating that no major changes in the hydrogen bonding in the helices takes place when transmembrane potential ($E-E_{pzc}$) changes.

Figure 9. (a) PM IRRAS spectra determined for the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm (9:9:2) bilayer formed on the β -Tg-modified gold (111) electrode at several potentials vs. Ag/AgCl. The top spectrum corresponds to the spectrum of a randomly oriented DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm film calculated from the IR transmission spectrum of the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm (9:9:2) vesicle solution. (b) The deconvolution result of the amide I region showing 5 distinct vibrations corresponding to different secondary structures.

The integrated intensity of the α -helix and 3_{10} -helix bands provide information about the orientation of the axes of the two helices with respect to the bilayer normal.^{24,25} Figure S8 of the Supporting Information defines graphically the tilt angle of the helices and the text below Figure S8 provides detailed information how the tilt angles of the helices were calculated. Figure 10 (a) presents the tilt angles of the two helices with respect to the surface normal as a function of applied potential. These angles were calculated using the procedure described in ref^{24,25} and

explained in Figure S8 of the Supporting Information. For comparison, the membrane resistivity determined from EIS measurements is plotted in Figure 10 (b). The tilt angles of the helices decrease as the potential is moved from 0.1 to -0.3 V vs Ag/AgCl and then increases at more negative potentials. These changes show excellent correlation with the shape of the differential capacitance curve in Figure 1. The increase of the tilt angles at -0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl corresponds to the onset of desorption (detachment) of the membrane from the electrode surface. Consequently, the electrolyte penetrates into the space between the membrane and the gold surface. As a result, the voltage drop takes place across this sub-membrane layer meaning that the membrane is losing the effect of charge on the metal. The minimum values of the tilt angle of $\sim 10^\circ$ and 22° correspond well with the inserted state of alamethicin molecules whose helices assume a small tilt with respect to surface normal.

Figure 10 (a) Dependence of tilt angles of main axes of the α -helix (red circles) and 3_{10} -helix (black triangles) of alamethicin molecules embedded in the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm (9:9:2) bilayer formed on the β -Tg-modified Au (111) electrode as a function of applied potential. (b) Membrane resistance of the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm bilayer at different potentials measured by EIS.

The top horizontal axis in Figure 10 plots $E-E_{pzc}$. The values of the tilt angles of the two helices are significantly smaller than 90° even at E_{pzc} indicating that alamethicin molecules are already inserted into the bilayer when charge density at the gold electrode surface is equal to zero. This correlates well with low membrane resistance of the bilayer at this potential in the presence of alamethicin shown in Table 1. Furthermore, the tilt of the two helices is significantly smaller in the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm floating bilayer, which contains negatively charged lipids, than in the DPhPC/Alm bilayer composed of zwitterionic lipids. This point is illustrated by Figures 11 (a) and (b), which compare the tilt angles of the α -helix and 3_{10} -helix in the two bilayers as a function of $E-E_{pzc}$. This presentation corrects the data for differences in E_{pzc} of the gold electrode in the presence of the two bilayers. The differences between the two films are significant and show that alamethicin is inserted much easier into the negatively charged bilayer than the neutral bilayer composed of zwitterionic lipids. Most significantly, the data show that alamethicin is inserted into the negatively charged DMPC/Egg-PG membrane at potentials close to E_{pzc} , but not into the zwitterionic DPhPC/Alm. This behavior is consistent with the antibiotic properties of alamethicin in nature. It demonstrates that these peptides have a higher affinity towards the membrane of a bacterial cell than that of mammalian cell.

Figure 11. Comparison of tilt angles of primary axes of (a) the α -helix and (b) 3_{10} -helix of alamethicin molecules embedded into the DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm (9:9:2) [red circles] and DPhPC/Alm (9:1) [black squares] bilayers floating on the β -Tg-modified gold (111) electrode as a function of applied potential in a 0.1 M NaF electrolyte solution.

Summary and Conclusions

We have performed concerted EIS, AFM and PM-IRRAS studies of the insertion of alamethicin into the negatively charged DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer floating on the β -thioglucose modified gold surface. The EIS measurements demonstrated that insertion of alamethicin into the

DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer causes about an order of magnitude decrease of the membrane resistivity. The membrane resistivity was further decreased with applied negative potentials. The AFM images show that alamethicin molecules inserted into the bilayer form porous nanocluster aggregates within the phospholipid matrix where pore diameters were 2.0 ± 0.2 nm. The peptide insertion removes stress in the bilayer and assists in the formation of a more uniform film. The results of PM-IRRAS measurements provided strong evidence that alamethicin molecules insert into the membrane assuming a small angle between α -helix and the surface normal. The small tilt angle of α -helix is consistent with the barrel stave model of the pore.¹⁴ The decrease of the tilt angle with negative potential correlated well with the decrease of the membrane resistivity. The present for results for DMPC/Egg-PG fBLM are in a good agreement with recent SEIRAS study of alamethicin incorporation into a sparsely tethered bilayer with the top leaflet composed of a mixture of POPC and POPG.²³ The potential dependent tilt angle data for helices in DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer were compared to the values of tilt angles of helices of Alm in the DPhPC bilayer composed of zwitterionic lipids. The tilt angles of the helices were smaller in the negatively charged than in the zwitterionic bilayer. The tilt angle data demonstrated that alamethicin molecules are inserted into the DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer at E_{pzfc} . In contrast, the peptide assumes an inactive surface state at E_{pzfc} of the electrode with DPhPC bilayer. The results of this work demonstrate that alamethicin can discriminate between bacterial and mammalian membranes. In 0.1M NaF solution with pH~8.3 alamethicin has zero net charge and a dipole moment of $\sim 70D$. The negative charge of the dipole is on the C-terminus which is hydrophilic and positive charge at N-terminus which is hydrophobic.²⁸ The voltage gated insetion of alamethicin into the membrane is driven by hydrophobic interactions with the interior of the membrane and by dipole-field interactions when the negative charge is at the metal surface. Consequently, alamethicin enters the gold supported bilayer with its N-terminus. As discussed by Forbig et al²³, preferential insertion of alamethicin into a membrane that contains negatively charged PG head-groups is facilitated by repulsive interaction of negative charge at C-terminus with the negatively charged head-groups of the distal leaflet and attractive interaction between the positive charge at N-terminus and negatively charged head-groups of the proximal leaflet.

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Supporting Information

The immersion current transients; free charge versus potential plots, optical constants for the amide I band of alamethicin, EIS data of the DMPC/Egg-PG floating bilayer at different potentials; numerical values of the elements in the equivalent circuit of the DMPC/Egg-PG bilayer; AFM topography images of DMPC/Egg-PG/Alm (9:9:2) at (a) +0.1, (b) -0.1, (c) -0.2, (d) -0.3, (e) -0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl; impedance data showing reversibility of the bilayer properties due to a potential change; position of centers of amide I bands corresponding to α -helix and 3_{10} -helix as a function of applied potential; explanation of the procedure used to calculate the tilt angle of α -helix and 3_{10} -helix with respect to surface normal.

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